

Resource Sheet

Research Software and NRENs in Asia

Episode 1: Connecting NRENs and Research Software in Asia

Session information

Webpage	https://rse-asia.github.io/RSE_Asia/event/2026-02-10_ep-1-apan_conversation/
Date	11 February 2026
Time	07:00 - 08:00 am UTC (see in your time zone)
Facilitators	Jyoti Bhogal Saranjeet Kaur Bhogal
Guest	Liana Jacinta Jaganathan

Important links

- [Registration link - Episode 2: Research Software and Environmental Research in Asia](#)
- [RSE Asia survey link](#)
- RSE Asia [Community Membership form](#)

Resources and info from us

RSE Asia

- Website: https://rse-asia.github.io/RSE_Asia/
- For the latest news, events, activities, and opportunities, follow us on our [LinkedIn page](#)
- To join the RSE Asia community, please fill out our short [Community Membership Form](#)

Shared resources from the session

- Organisations
 - [Malaysian Research and Education Network \(MYREN\)](#)
 - [APAN](#)
 - [GÉANT](#)
- APAN working groups:
 - [Open Science Collaborative and Resource \(OSCR\)](#)
 - [HPC-AI working group](#)
 - [Asia Pacific Research Platform \(APRP\) working group](#)
- Programming, data analysis, and certifications:
 - For those who miss the convenience of dplyr syntax in Python:
 - <https://ibis-project.org/>
 - <https://siuba.org/>
 - [GreenDISC certifications](#) for writing green softwares
 - [Kaggle](#) - for open data and drawing insights
- Connection within the Asia Pacific, Europe and the US
 - [Civil Protection Department](#) from France
 - [AFoCO](#)
 - [Korean Forest Services](#) from Korea
 - [GÉANT Community Programme](#)
- Conferences/workshops/events:
 - [APAN meetings](#)
 - [AsiaConnect](#)
 - APAN workshops, like the [AP-GAINED](#) workshop during the APAN meetings
- Any questions for APAN: sec@apan.net

Upcoming events from around the world

- [ISGC2026](#), 15-20 March 2026, Taipei, Taiwan